

A Study on Consumers Buying Behaviour Towards Fmcg Products with Reference to Coimbatore District

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Abstract- This study highlighted that consumers place greater value on the quality of fast-moving consumer items when making purchases from particular brands. This study determines how much different factors affect the respondents' decisions to buy FMCG items. FMCG branding has become an essential element of consumers' daily lives. Every day, consumers are actually faced with hundreds of companies. This was accomplished by determining the primary factors of branding, quality, and the four Ps (price, packing, promotion, and purity). The study found that customers rely on branding and product quality, with the remaining factors having the least influence. Even while rural customers use their popular branded items across all product categories and spend a significant amount of their income on them, these products are now typically consumed by all cultures. While reducing the possibility that customers may favour certain companies because they are well-known to them or because of ads. This study also shows that, despite their modest participation with some items, customers form their attitudes and behaviours toward FMCG brands. Despite a number of complaints, it was effective in instilling brand ideals in the brains of its customers.

Keywords: FMCG, Brand, Rural Consumers, Consumer Behaviour, buying behaviour, customer satisfaction, consumer awareness.

I. INTRODUCTION

FAST MOVING CONSUMERS are those that purchase things on a regular or frequent basis, such as daily necessities. products that are inexpensive and sell rapidly.

The FMCG industry, which includes packaged foods, toiletries, detergents, shampoos, toothpaste, shaving products, shoe polish, household accessories, and some electronic goods, is one of the sectors of the Indian economy that is growing the fastest. These products have a high return rate and are intended for daily or regular usage. Given that India's per capita consumption of FMCG items is lower than that of other industrialised nations, the FMCG business has a lot.

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are heavily concentrated in urban and rural regions since one of the main drivers of the Indian market's expansion is the middle-class population's rapid

income rise. Packaging is a crucial component in the FMCG industry. To maximise efficiency, packing is frequently the primary and secondary step in the physical distribution process. In addition to offering information and sales incentives to higher customers, the unit packaging is essential for product protection. Despite having a relatively low profit margin, FMCG items are typically sold in enormous quantities, which can result in a significant cumulative profit. FMCG is a prime example of a high volume, poor profit business.

List of Top 10 FMCG Companies in India

1. Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL)
2. ITC Limited
3. Dabur India Ltd
4. Britannia Industries
5. Godrej Consumer Products Limited (GCPL)
6. Parle
7. Amul
8. Pidilite Industries
9. Patanjali Ayurved
10. Haldiram's

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sulekha and Kiran (2013) highlighted that over 72% of India's population resides in rural areas, making it a highly promising market for FMCG companies, especially as rural incomes rise and consumers increasingly seek lifestyle-enhancing products. This shift requires companies to design targeted marketing strategies based on region-specific rural buying behavior, as explored in their study across districts in Haryana. Similarly, Deliya (2012) emphasized the critical role of packaging in influencing consumer decisions, noting that packaging serves as a key communication tool by providing essential product information and reinforcing brand identity at the point of purchase. It plays a vital role in shaping consumer perceptions and purchase outcomes.

Tauseef (2011) focused on impulsive buying behavior in the FMCG retail sector in India, identifying factors such as promotions, product placement, pricing strategies, and merchandising as major influences. Based on primary data collected from retail outlets in Jodhpur and analyzed using factor analysis, the study found that rising incomes and changing lifestyles, influenced by western trends, have significantly increased consumers' purchasing power and impulse buying tendencies.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the profile of the FMCG products
- To know the brand awareness of the consumers
- To find out the level of preference among FMCG products

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This issue is picked among consumer aspects, the consumer attitude programs among FMCG items in Karur District, as these programs have been becoming better every day everywhere, notably in this organization. The Convince Sampling approach was employed for this investigation. There was use of both primary and secondary data.

Data Analysis

The statistical tools are used to analyze the primary data collected from the above primary data collected. This involves a lot of calculation and computations. The following analyses were used, namely Frequency tables, and Rank test were used to find the preferences of the FMCG products.

Limitations of the Study:

Since the study was taken only in Coimbatore with covering only major five areas only, so the results and conclusion may not be applicable to other areas. This study limited to the branded products of the FMCG.

The study based upon the opinions expressed only by the respondents of those particular areas

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Satisfaction Level of Consumers

Overall Satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	58	23.2
Satisfied	51	20.4
Neutral	67	26.8
Dissatisfied	44	17.6
Highly Dissatisfied	30	12
Total	250	100

Preference Towards FMCG Products

S.No	FMCG Items	Mean	Rank
1	Tooth Paste	5.88	9
2	Shampoo	2.83	3
3	Hair Oil	5.22	8
4	Face Powder	6.03	10
5	Soap	4.63	7
6	Chocolates	1.54	1
7	Noodles	1.91	2
8	Biscuit	2.89	4
9	Cleaners	4.16	5
10	Cool Drinks	3.21	6

Majority of the sample respondents i.e., 54% are male, Nearly one-third of the sample respondents i.e., 26.4% are aged between 36-45 years and 38.8 %

of the sample respondents are qualified Under Graduates in their qualification. In addition to that, Nearly 30% of the sample respondents are professionals in their Occupation. The .32 % of the sample respondents are getting awareness of consuming FMCG products through Television.

Satisfaction Level of the Consumers

1. 27% of the sample respondents are NEUTRALLY getting satisfied about the satisfaction level.
2. Respondents Preference on FMCG Products.
3. The top preferred FMCG items are founded through Rank Test.
4. It can also be found that the high ranking FMCG item is "Chocolates".
5. Hence, the respondents have preferences through 'Chocolates', 'Cool Drinks', and 'Shampoo' as the first three choices on purchasing FMCG items.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the success of many businesses depends on their ability to attract and retain customers. Companies must focus on offering products at reasonable prices, maintaining good quality, and ensuring the availability of their brands across all stores to both retain existing customers and attract new ones. Brand loyalty serves as a powerful competitive advantage, helping companies stand out in the marketplace. The FMCG sector in India is highly dynamic, with a primary objective of effectively satisfying the needs and wants of consumers while targeting markets efficiently. Therefore, the insights from this study will help companies refine their marketing strategies and enhance their ability to serve customers better.

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